

EFFECTS OF VALUES INTEGRATION ON THE BEHAVIOR AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 8 STUDENTS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANGONO, RIZAL

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Effects of Values Integration on the Behavior and Academic Performance of Grade 8 Students in Public Secondary Schools in Angono, Rizal

Mary Grace M. Reyes*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study aimed to determine the effects of values integration on the behavior and academic performance of grade 8 students in selected public secondary schools in Angono, Rizal during the School Year 2019-2020. The respondents of the study were selected grade 8 students in public secondary schools in Angono, Rizal. The sample size was determined through the Slovin's formula. Hence out of 1928 students, 321 were considered. Simple random sampling technique was used in the selection of the respondents. Descriptive survey research design was applied utilizing a researcher-made questionnaire-checklist in gathering the needed data on the effects of values integration on the behavior of grade 8 students with respect to overt and covert behavior. Documentary analysis was also applied since the average grades of the students in the previous school year were obtained as basis of their academic performance. The study revealed that Values integration has less effects on the behavior of Grade 8 students with respect to overt behavior and covert behavior. Monthly family income and fathers' educational attainment are greatly significant to the effects of values integration on the behavior of the students with respect to overt behavior and covert behavior; however, when grouped by age, sex, sibling position, number of children in the family and mothers' educational attainment is not significant. The student performs satisfactory as revealed by their average grades. Moreso, there is significant relationship between the perceived extent of effects of values integration on the behavior of the respondents and their academic performance. The study concluded that monthly family income and fathers' educational attainment are determinants on the effects of values integration on the behavior of the Grade 8 students. It was recommended that teachers and parents may go hand in hand in monitoring closely the behavior of students for effective values integration.

Keywords: *values integration, behavior, academic performance*

Introduction

Education is a systematic and a planned process of the development of the potential of a being to its maximum. It is considered as a major vehicle for inculcation of values among children. It is a process of transmission of values, which helps them to lead a good life, in accordance with societal aims.

Values form an integral part of the school curriculum. Values are related to both the cognitive and affective domains of human behavior. Schools play a large role in teaching the next generation how to be successful members of the society then every precaution should be taken to make sure that effects of values development on the behavioral and academic performance of students is one that help students thrive.

Several programs have been launched by the government eyeing at the development of the educational processes from the students up to the educator's personality. The DepEd Values Education Program, gears mainly in translating values from the abstract into the practical. The importance behind this program is that when values are subjected into a book or in a classroom seems to be in abstract way, but its effectiveness is said to be true when such values are transmitted to real life.

In public secondary schools, values education is integrated in teaching the different subjects. Integration of values education in the different subjects depends on how students are taught on positive ways and are provided a list of principles, pillars, values or virtues, which are memorized or around which themed activities are planned. It is commonly claimed that the values included in any list are universally recognized. Integration of values education in the different subjects depends for its success on the teacher's creativity in making use of the situation to facilitate the student's values development. With many cases of bullying and misbehavior of pupils inside and outside the classroom, the researcher conceived this study to determine the extent of effects of values integration on the behavior and academic performance of grade 8 students in public secondary schools.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the effects of values integration on the behavior and academic performance of grade 8 students in selected public secondary schools in Angono, Rizal during the School Year 2019-2020. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following sub – problems:

1. What is the profile of the selected grade 8 students in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. sibling position;

- 1.4. number of children in the family;
- 1.5. monthly family income; and
- 1.6. parents' educational attainment
2. What is the extent of effects of values integration on the behavior of grade 8 students as perceived by themselves with respect to:
 - 2.1. overt behavior; and
 - 2.2. covert behavior?
3. Is there significant difference on the extent of effects of values integration on the behavior of grade 8 students with the respect to the cited aspects in terms of their profile?
4. What is the level of academic performance of the respondents as revealed by their average grades?
5. Is there significant relationship between the perceived extent of effects of values integration on the behavior of the respondents and their academic performance?

Literature Review

According to Gaikwad (2014), values are related to both the cognitive and affective domains of human behavior. The need for integration of values in the curricular transactions of the school has been expressed and emphasized. Value orientation needs to be integrated into the curricular and co-curricular programs of the school. The teaching approaches and strategies should be structured in a way that students inculcate values.

Relatively, Groove (2016) cited that Values-based Education is an approach to teaching that works with values. It creates a strong learning environment that enhances academic achievement and develops students' social and relationship skills that last throughout their lives. The positive learning environment is achieved through the positive values modelled by staff throughout the school.

In addition, Wynne (2017) confirmed that values-based schools emphasize value education in their curriculum and teaching. Therefore, students become academically more diligent, the schools acquire a more peaceful ambience, better student-teacher relationships are forged, student and teacher wellbeing improve, and parents are more engaged with the school.

Also, according to Tucker (2018), teaching values in public schools is advantageous if the values do not infringe on religious or personal beliefs. Some values, such as honesty and fairness, are universal, but others are specific to an individual's personal beliefs and are not appropriate for the classroom.

Meanwhile, Sulayman (2013) stated that children learn values through different sources like home, school, religion, media and other influences on which they are exposed. The values learnt from different sources have a lasting impact on the children and shape their personality.

Calderon (2015) cited that the approach of the formal curriculum for value integration is direct and explicit. The influences of the informal or non-formal curriculum are implicit and more profound. They are often more effective than the formal teaching of lessons. Many schools provide opportunities of informal activities by organizing events which involve social action, service in the community, raising funds for good causes.

Marini (2017) conducted a study to find out about implementation of character values integration in school culture at elementary schools in Jakarta. The result showed that means of character values integration in religious, honesty, discipline, clean and healthy, tolerance, working ethos, and nationalism culture were achieved from theoretically maximum scores. This study concluded that character values has already been integrated effectively in religious, discipline, clean and healthy, tolerance, working ethos, and nationalism culture at 63 elementary schools in Jakarta.

Furthermore, Nuevo (2016) determined the extent of exercise of the core values along Maka-Diyos (Godly), Makatao (mindful of humanity), makakalikasan (respectful of nature) and Makabansa (patriotic and nationalistic) and the extent of integration of such by the Grades Five and Six Social Studies teachers in the District of Bolinao, Pangasinan, Philippines and find out the relationship between the extent of exercise and integration of the core values. It was found evident that there is a high or very high relationship between the extent of exercise and extent of integration of the core values along Maka-Diyos, Makatao, Makakalikasan and Makabansa by the Grades Five and Six Social Studies teachers in the District of Bolinao. Hence, the teachers' exercise of the core values affects the quality of their integration of the core values in their teaching.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed the descriptive method of research utilizing a questionnaire-checklist in gathering the needed data. Specifically, descriptive survey research design was applied. Calmorin (2016) asserted that descriptive research is concerned with conditions and relationships that exists, practices that prevail, beliefs and process that are going on, effects or trends that are being developed.

The cited research design is appropriate to the present study since the aim is to determine the effects of values integration on the

behavior and academic performance of grade 8 students in public secondary schools in Angono Rizal.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were selected grade 8 students in selected public secondary schools in Angono, Rizal. The sample size was determined using the Slovin's formula. Random sampling technique was used in the selection of the respondents. They were described in terms of age, sex, sibling position, number of children in the family, monthly family income and parents' educational att

Instrument

The study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire-checklist as the main instrument in gathering the needed data. Part I dealt with the personal data of the respondents in terms of age, sex, sibling position, number of children in the family, monthly family income and parents' educational attainment. Part II focused on the extent of effects of values integration on the behavior of grade 8 students as perceived by themselves with respect to overt and covert behavior.

Procedure

The study followed the Gantt Chart of Activities in the conduct of the study. This includes the formulation of research problem up to the revision of the manuscript and submission of the final copy. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent. After the validation of the instrument, the questionnaire-checklist was administered to the respondents through Google survey form.

After the retrieval, the data were encoded and processed. Data were analyzed and interpreted based on the sub problems. Summary of findings, conclusions and recommendations were formulated. After the oral defense, the manuscript was revised considering the comments and suggestions of the Oral Examination Committee. After finalization, hard bound copies were submitted to the office of the Graduate Studies Program and other concerned offices.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Profile of the Grade 8 Students in Terms of the Selected Variables

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of the Selected Variables*

Age	F	%
17 years old	25	7.8
16 years old	11	3.4
15 years old	41	12.8
14 years old	244	76.0
Total	321	100
Sex	F	%
Male	133	41.43
Female	188	58.57
Total	321	100
Sibling Position	F	%
1st born	115	35.8
2nd born	94	29.3
3rd born	41	12.8
4th born	24	10.6
5th born and above	37	11.5
Total	321	100
Number of Children in the Family	F	%
Four and above	140	43.61
Three	83	25.86
Two	52	16.20
One	46	14.33
Total	321	100
Monthly Family Income	F	%
₱20,000 and above	58	18.07
₱15,000 - ₱19,999	53	16.51
₱10,000 - ₱14,999	72	22.42
Below ₱10,000	139	43.30
Total	321	100
Parent's Educational Attainment	Father	Mother
	f %	f %

College Graduate	74	23.1	60	18.7
College Undergraduate	55	17.1	75	23.4
High School Graduate	127	39.6	124	38.6
High School Undergraduate	65	20.2	62	19.3
Total	321	100	321	100

The table shows that among the 321 respondents, there are 244 or 76.0 percent who belong to 14 years old; followed by 41 or 12.8 percent who aged 15 years old and 17 years old with 25 or 7.8 percent and the least is 16 years old with only 11 or 3.4 percent. Majority of them are females with 188 or 58.57 percent over males with 133 or 41.43 percent, who are 1st and 2nd born child with 115 or 35.8 percent and 04 or 29.3 percent respectively. Most of the respondents' family have four and above children with 140 or 43.61 percent and the least is an only child in the family with 46 or 14.33 percent, with several of them have monthly family income of below Php10,000.00; followed by 72 or 22.42 percent with monthly family income of Php 10,000 – Php 14,999 and the least is with monthly family income of Php 15,000 – Php 19,999 at 53 or 16.51 percent. As to their parent's educational attainment, most of the fathers are high school graduate with 127 or 39.6 percent and college graduate with 74 or 23.1 percent while most of the mothers are high school graduate with 124 or 38.6 percent and college undergraduate with 75 or 23.4 percent respectively.

Effects of Values Integration on the Behavior of Grade 8 Students as Perceived by Themselves

Table 2. *Extent of Effects of Values Integration on the Behavior of the Respondents as Perceived by Themselves with Respect to Overt Behavior*

Overt Behavior	WX	VI
<i>Values integration in school encourages me to ...</i>		
1. learn how to respond to new and unfamiliar situations at the same time	2.22	Less
2. handle stressful and challenging circumstances	2.41	Less
3. gain experience managing stressful situations and gain confidence while doing so	2.46	Less
4. show strong feelings and intense emotions at different times.	2.42	Less
5. make my own decisions and face the consequences.	2.46	Less
6. decide which family values will be integrated to my own set of beliefs and values.	2.46	Less
7. look for new experiences: and engage in more risk-taking behavior	2.36	Less
8. communicate in different ways using the internet, cell phones and social media	2.14	Less
9. learn to balance multiple relationships that compete for time, energy, and attention	2.16	Less
10. create and maintain social bonds in completely different ways:	2.21	Less
Overall WX	2.33	Less

The table shows that with respect to overt behavior, the overall weighted mean of 2.33 verbally interpreted as less. All items are verbally interpreted as less. It can be deduced from the findings that the overt behavior as values integration less affects the behavior of the respondents.

This implies that students believe that values integration in school encourage the students to gain experience managing stressful situations and gain confidence while doing so and they make their own decisions and fact the consequences.

This finding is supported by the statements of Marquez (2018) that children learn values through different sources like home, school, religion, media and other influences on which they are exposed.

Table 3. *Extent of Effects of Values Integration on the Behavior of the Respondents as Perceived by Themselves with Respect to Covert Behavior*

Covert Behavior	WX	VI
<i>Values integration in school helps me to ...</i>		
1. focus thinking on making decisions.	2.07	Less
2. think more about “right” and “wrong” and develop a stronger individual set of values and morals	2.15	Less
3. enhance myself awareness and the ability to reflect on one’s own being.	2.13	Less
4. apply my new reflective capabilities to moral issues.	2.32	Less
5. use more complex thinking focused on personal decision-making in school and at home.	2.34	Less
6. manage stressful situations and gain confidence while doing so.	2.36	Less
7. expand thinking to include more philosophical and futuristic concerns.	2.32	Less
8. use systematic thinking and influence relationships with others.	2.58	Moderate
9. use complex thinking to focus on less self-centered concepts and personal decision-making.	2.30	Less
10. increase thoughts about more global concepts, such as justice, history, science, health, and patriotism.	2.21	Less
Overall WX	2.28	Less

The table reflects that with respect to covert behavior, the overall weighted mean obtained is 2.28 verbally interpreted as less. Nine items are verbally interpreted as less while only one item is verbally interpreted as moderate. It can be noted from the findings that the covert behavior as values integration less affects the behavior of the respondents. This could only mean that as student believed, values integration in school helps them to manage stressful situations and gain confidence while doing so and use more complex thinking

focused on personal decision-making in school and at home.

This finding is related to the citation of Calderon (2015) that the approach of the formal curriculum for value integration is direct and explicit. The influences of the informal or non-formal curriculum are implicit and more profound.

Significant Difference on the Extent of Effects of Values Integration on the Behavior of the Respondents with Respect to the Different Aspects in Terms of Their Profile

Table 4. *Computed F-values on the Extent of Effects of Values Integration on the Behavior of the Respondents with Respect to the Different Aspects in Terms of Their Profile*

Aspects	F-comp	p-values	Ho	VI
Age				
Overt Behavior	0.141	.935	Accepted	Not Significant
Covert Behavior	1.142	.332	Accepted	Not Significant
Sex				
Overt Behavior	0.233	.874	Accepted	Not Significant
Covert Behavior	1.206	.308	Accepted	Not Significant
Sibling Position				
Overt Behavior	0.626	.644	Accepted	Not Significant
Covert Behavior	0.481	.749	Accepted	Not Significant
Number of Children in the Family				
Overt Behavior	0.604	.660	Accepted	Not Significant
Covert Behavior	1.598	.175	Accepted	Not Significant
Monthly Family Income				
Overt Behavior	2.958	.003	Rejected	Significant
Covert Behavior	2.789	.041	Rejected	Significant
Father's Educational Attainment				
Overt Behavior	4.620	.005	Rejected	Significant
Covert Behavior	2.896	.035	Rejected	Significant
Mother's Educational Attainment				
Overt Behavior	2.030	.110	Accepted	Not Significant
Covert Behavior	2.073	.104	Accepted	Not Significant

The tabulated data showed that variation on the extent of effects of the values integration on the behavior of the respondents with respect to over behavior and covert behavior are greatly affected by their monthly family income and father's educational attainment since the computed p-values are less than the .05 level of significance, thus rejects the null hypothesis. However, in terms of age, sex, sibling position, number of children in the family and mother's educational attainment, there is no distinctive difference is apparent since the p-values is more than .05 probability values, thus the null hypothesis is accepted.

Findings imply that the differences in their personal characteristics are significantly affected by the values integration on the behavior of the students. Thus, strong financial status and higher educational attainment helps improve students' behavior.

This is congruent to the conclusion of the study of Hajilan (2017), that the demographic variables did not significantly influence both behavioral and instructional management practices except for the monthly income which shows significant relationship to instructional management practices.

Level of Academic Performance of the Respondents as Revealed by the Their Average Grades

Table 5. *Level of Academic Performance of Student Recipients as Revealed by the Their Average Grades*

Average Grades	Verbal Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
85-89	Very Satisfactory	37	11
80-84	Satisfactory	181	57
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	103	32
Total		321	100
Mean	81.02 (Satisfactory)		
Standard Deviation	3.140		

It can be seen from the table that the highest frequency of 181 and a percentage of 57 shows that many of the students obtained an average grade of 80-84 percent verbally interpreted Satisfactory; followed by 181 or 57 percent with obtained average grades of 75-79% verbally interpreted Fairly Satisfactory and 37 or 11 percent are with an average grade of 85-89% verbally interpreted Very Satisfactory. The mean obtained is 81.02 and standard deviation of 3.140.

This means that the students have satisfactory academic performance as revealed by their average grades. This only means that the students performed well in the class due to the integration of values in teaching on their overt behavior and covert behavior.

This is supported by the study of Kausar (2017), that a well-managed and vibrant classroom environment has a positive effect on the academic achievement of students in the subject of Pakistan studies at secondary level.

Significant Relationship Between the Perceived Extent of Effects of Values Integration on the Behavior of the Respondents and their Academic Performance

Table 6. *Computed r-value on the Relationship Between the Perceived Extent of Effects of Values Integration on the Behavior of the Respondents and their Academic Performance*

<i>Extent of the Behavior Category</i>	<i>r-values</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Ho</i>	<i>VI</i>
Overt Behavior	.446	.000	Rejected	Significant
Covert Behavior	.008	.890	Accepted	Not Significant

It can be seen from the table that statistical results indicate that the p-value obtained for the test of significant relationship between the perceived extent of effects of values integration on the behavior of the respondents with respect to over behavior and their academic performance, yielded p-value lower than .05 level of significant, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. However, with respect to covert behavior, the results indicate that p-value is more than .05 level of significant, thus accepts the null hypothesis.

Findings imply a correlation between the perceived effects of values integration on the behavior of the students and their academic performance. This only means that the student's over behavior is affected by the integration of values in school, thus improve their academic performance.

The findings are related with the results in the study of Nuevo (2016), that there is a high or very high relationship between the extent of exercise and extent of integration of the core values along Maka-Diyos, Makatao, Makakalikasan and Makabansa.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

Month family income and fathers' educational attainment are determinants on the effects of values integration on the behavior of the Grade 8 students.

There is significant correlation between the perceived effects of values integration on the behavior of students and their academic performance.

It can be noted from the findings that the covert behavior as values integration less affects the behavior of the respondents. This could only mean that as student believed, values integration in school helps them to manage stressful situations and gain confidence while doing so and use more complex thinking focused on personal decision-making in school and at home. This further connotes that integrating values in school help the students to apply the new reflective capabilities to moral issues and expand their thinking to include more philosophical and futuristic concerns.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Mary Grace M. Reyes

Dr. Vivencio B. Villamayor Integrated School

Department of Education – Philippines